

Effects on the Frequency and Intensity of the Stretching Vibration of the Nitrile Group on Ligation to Metal Ions

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The infrared frequencies and intensities of the $C\equiv N$ stretching vibration for mononuclear complexes of dinitriles coordinated to a series of pentaammine metal centers have been measured. The uncomplexed nitrile function acts as an internal standard against which the changes in frequency and intensity on ligation can be measured. The frequency of the ligated nitrile decreases in the order Co^{III} , Rh^{III} ; Ru^{III} ; Ir^{III} ; Os^{III} ; Ru^{II} ; Os^{II} , which is rather closely followed for each of the four dinitriles studied. When the ratio of the integrated intensity of the absorption of the bound nitrile to the remote nitrile is ranked in the same order, there is a decline from values in the range of 3–7 to a minimum at Os^{III} , whereupon it increases very sharply for some of the dinitriles. In the case of two of the dinitriles, the intensity of the bands of the nitrile ligated to Os^{III} is so low that the absorption was not observed. An analysis of the data suggests that two major effects are responsible for the effect of the metal ions on the properties of the infrared absorption. For Ru^{II} and Os^{II} , back-bonding is the major influence; for cases there is in addition the effect of the metal ions in engaging the donor electron pair of the nitrogen. A qualitative treatment of the effects arising from these interactions however does not suffice for a detailed explanation of the changes observed.

IN the course of studies on rates of intramolecular electron transfer, pentaammine complexes of Ru^{III} and Co^{III} with the isomers of dicyanobenzenes were prepared¹. The changes in infrared frequencies and in intensities which we observed in characterising the compounds suggested significant interrelationships which have seemed worthy of systematic exploration. We were additionally motivated to this kind of study by experience in a different investigation², which involved the interaction of acetone with pentaammineosmium(III) and pentaamminecobalt(III). The $C=O$ frequency for acetone bound to Co^{III} is quite intense and the absence of a signal for the pentaammineosmium(III) salt recovered from a solution of the trifluoromethanesulphonate salt in acetone led us to conclude that Os^{III} brings about a rapid condensation of acetone, liberating water and forming aquopentaammineosmium(III). Further study of the system however revealed that the condensation brought about by $(NH_3)_5Os^{III}$ is quite slow, and we are faced with the fact that the carbonyl stretching frequency for acetone coordinated to osmium(III) is very much less than when it is coordinated to cobalt(III).

In the study described herein we have capitalised on the strategy that was inadvertently hit upon in the earlier work¹ on mononuclear complexes of dinitriles: the uncomplexed nitrile in the mononuclear pentaammine complexes serves as an internal standard, greatly facilitating assessing the effect of complex formation on the frequency and intensity of the $C\equiv N$ stretching vibrations. The interpretation of the results is further simplified because we have restricted the comparison at this stage to the

pentaammine complexes, so that the different metal centers have the same environment. We do acknowledge that valuable additional insight is to be gained by judicious variations of the composition of the auxiliary ligands. In view of the conclusions we have reached on the major role played by back-bonding, replacement of NH_3 , which acts as a simple electron donor, by π acid ligands such as pyridine which compete for πd electron density³, seems particularly worthwhile.

Acronyms: DCB(dicyanobenzene), FN(fumeronitrile), GN(glutaronitrile), DBO(1,4-dicyanobicyclo[2.2.2]octane).

Experimental

Glutaronitrile, succinonitrile and 1,2-, 1,3- and 1,4-dicyanobenzene (Aldrich) were used. 1,3-Dicyanobenzene was recrystallised from ethanol. The other nitriles were used as received.

Most of the nitrile complexes were prepared by the reaction of the nitrile ligand with the trifluoromethanesulphonates of the pentaammine complexes in a poorly coordinating solvent. These were synthesised according to the reported methods^{3,4}.

Non-aqueous solvents were dried and stored over molecular sieves. The product complexes were stored under vacuum in a desiccator to minimise exposure to atmospheric water. Of all the complexes studied, those of Ru^{III} are the most susceptible to hydrolysis, but even in these cases no effects attributable to hydrolysis were observed¹.

Preparation of nitrile complexes :

The syntheses of the 1,2-, 1,3- and 1,4-dicyanobenzene complexes of a given metal were similar, and the synthesis of the corresponding glutaronitrile complex differed only in the quantity of ligand used. Generalised syntheses are outlined below.

$[Ru^{III}(NH_3)_5(dinitrile)](CF_3SO_3)_3$: These were prepared according to the method of Schäffer¹. The dinitrile ligand (DCB, 1.0 g; GN, 1 ml) was dissolved in propylene carbonate (10 ml) with mild heating. A solution of $[Ru(NH_3)_5(CF_3SO_3)](CF_3SO_3)_2$ (0.10 g) in propylene carbonate (3 ml) was added. The mixture was heated at 70° with stirring for 2 h. The solution was cooled to room temperature, then diluted with acetone (10 ml). Diethyl ether was added gradually with vigorous shaking until a solid formed. The solid was filtered, washed with ether and dried under reduced pressure (60–70 mg, 50–60%); the DCB complexes, light yellow; the GN complex, white.

$[Ru^{II}(NH_3)_5(dinitrile)](CF_3SO_3)_2$: Separate solutions of $[Ru(NH_3)_5(CF_3SO_3)](CF_3SO_3)_2$ (90–100 mg) in acetone (5 ml) and the ligand (DCB, 300 mg; GN, 1 ml) in acetone (5 ml) were deaerated with argon in a Zwickel flask for 2 h. The argon was passed through a tower containing acetone to saturate it with solvent before it passed through the solutions. Zinc amalgam was added to the ruthenium solution and the Ru^{III} solution, originally pale yellow, turned deep orange within a few minutes. After the reduction proceeded for 30 min, the ruthenium solution was mixed anaerobically with the ligand solution. This gave an immediate colour change to red in the case of DCB or pale yellow in the case of GN. An hour after the solutions were mixed, the reaction mixture was transferred to an Erlenmeyer flask and diethyl ether added to precipitate a solid. The solid was filtered, washed with ether and dried under reduced pressure (65–90 mg, 70–90%); the 1,2- and 1,3-DCB complexes, bright orange; the 1,4-DCB complex, darker orange; the GN complex, pale yellow.

The DCB complexes were also prepared separately by the reduction of the corresponding ruthenium(III)(DCB) complexes. The reductions were performed under an argon atmosphere in a glove-box. $[Ru(NH_3)_5(DCB)](CF_3SO_3)_3$ (~15 mg) was dissolved in acetone (5 ml). Several pieces of magnesium turnings which had been freshly scraped with a metal spatula were added. The mixture was stirred for 2.5 h. Methylene chloride was then added to precipitate the product. The solid was filtered, washed with ether and dried under reduced pressure (~5 mg).

$[Os^{III}(NH_3)_5(dinitrile)](CF_3SO_3)_3$: The dinitrile ligand (DCB, 500 mg; GN, 1 ml) was dissolved in propylene carbonate (5–10 ml) with low heating. A solution of $[Os(NH_3)_5(CF_3SO_3)](CF_3SO_3)_2$ (100–200 mg) in propylene carbonate (3 ml) was added and the mixture stirred and heated at 70° for 4 h. The solution was cooled to room temperature

and diluted with acetone (10 ml). The product was precipitated by gradual addition of diethyl ether and filtered. The solid was redissolved in acetone, filtered and reprecipitated with ether. The solid was again filtered washed with ether and dried under reduced pressure to yield very light yellow product (90–115 mg, 65–80%).

$[Os^{II}(NH_3)_5(dinitrile)](CF_3SO_3)_2$: The Os^{II} compounds were prepared under argon in a glove-box. $[Os(NH_3)_5(dinitrile)](CF_3SO_3)_2$ (~20 mg) prepared as above was dissolved in acetone (5 ml). About 6 pieces of magnesium turnings whose surface had been scraped with a metal spatula were added to the solution, which was then stirred for 4 h. During this time the colour of the solution changed from yellow to dark green in the case of the dicyanobenzene complexes, or reddish purple in the glutaronitrile case. The solution was removed by pipette from the vial containing the magnesium and transferred to another vial. Diethyl ether was added to precipitate a solid. The solid was filtered and washed with ether (~5 mg); the glutaronitrile complex, light reddish purple; the DCB complexes, dark green. In each case the potassium bromide pellet was prepared immediately and the ir spectrum obtained.

$[Co(NH_3)_5(dinitrile)](CF_3SO_3)_3$: The compounds were prepared by the method of Schäffer¹. The ligand (DCB, 300 mg; GN, 0.5 ml) was dissolved in sulpholane (3 ml) with low heating. (When propylene carbonate was used as the solvent in these syntheses, intractable oils resulted.) A solution of $[Co(NH_3)_5(CF_3SO_3)](CF_3SO_3)_2$ (80 mg) in sulpholane (3 ml) was added. The mixture was stirred and heated at 70° for 3–4 h during which time the color changed from pink to orange. The solution was cooled to room temperature and diluted with acetone (10 ml). Diethyl ether was added to precipitate the product, which was then filtered. The product was redissolved in acetone, filtered and reprecipitated with ether. The resulting solid was filtered, washed with ether and dried under reduced pressure to yield light orange products (40–60 mg, 40–60%).

$[Rh(NH_3)_5(dinitrile)](CF_3SO_3)_3$: The ligand (DCB, 300 mg; GN, 1 ml) was dissolved in propylene carbonate (3 ml) with low heating. A solution of $[Rh(NH_3)_5(CF_3SO_3)](CF_3SO_3)_2$ (100 mg) in propylene carbonate (3 ml) was added. The mixture was heated to 70° and stirred for 6 h. After cooling to room temperature, it was diluted with acetone (10 ml) and the product precipitated with diethyl ether, then filtered. The solid was redissolved in acetone, filtered and then reprecipitated with ether. The resulting solid was filtered, washed with ether and dried under reduced pressure to yield white products (80 mg, 67%).

$[Ir(NH_3)_5(dinitrile)](CF_3SO_3)_3$: The ligand (DCB, 300 mg; GN, 1 ml) was dissolved in propylene carbonate (3 ml) with low heating. A solution of $[Ir(NH_3)_5(CF_3SO_3)](CF_3SO_3)_2$ (50 mg) in propylene carbonate (3 ml) was added. The mixture

was stirred at 70° for 4 h, then cooled to room temperature. The solution was diluted with acetone (10 ml) and the product precipitated by gradual addition of diethyl ether. The solid was filtered and redissolved in acetone. The solution was filtered and the product reprecipitated with ether. The resulting solid was filtered, washed with ether and dried under reduced pressure to yield white products (35–45 mg, 60–75%).

Purification: The compounds were recrystallised by vapour diffusion of diethyl ether into acetone solution. The recrystallisations were performed under argon in a glove-box. The microanalytical data are summarised in Table I. Because of the sensitivity of the Os^{II} complexes to air, no attempt was made to obtain microanalyses for them.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL DATA OF PENTAAMMINE-METAL TRIFLATES

Metal	Dinitrile	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
		C	H	N
Co	GN	13.90 (14.02)	3.11 (3.09)	13.19 (14.31)
	1,2-DCB	18.36 (18.37)	2.97 (2.66)	11.94 (13.63)
	1,3-DCB	18.65 (18.37)	3.10 (2.66)	12.06 (13.63)
	1,4-DCB	17.66 (18.37)	2.65 (2.66)	13.79 (13.63)
Rh	GN	13.19 (13.17)	2.92 (2.90)	13.37 (13.44)
	1,2-DCB	17.34 (17.51)	2.62 (2.51)	12.77 (12.84)
	1,3-DCB	17.51 (17.31)	2.77 (2.51)	11.92 (12.84)
	1,4-DCB	16.99 (17.31)	2.65 (2.51)	12.86 (12.84)
Ir	GN	11.70 (11.74)	2.52 (2.59)	11.88 (11.98)
	1,2-DCB	15.92 (15.49)	2.32 (2.25)	10.53 (11.50)
	1,3-DCB	15.46 (15.49)	2.36 (2.25)	11.25 (11.50)
	1,4-DCB	9.87 (15.49)	2.51 (2.25)	9.39 (11.50)
RuIII	GN	13.18 (13.21)	2.87 (2.91)	13.39 (13.48)
	1,2-DCB	16.96 (17.35)	2.80 (2.51)	11.94 (12.88)
	1,3-DCB	17.69 (17.35)	2.84 (2.51)	12.03 (12.88)
	1,4-DCB	16.75 (17.35)	2.48 (2.51)	12.53 (12.88)
OsIII	GN	8.69 (11.77)	2.48 (2.59)	10.50 (12.01)
	1,2-DCB	15.62 (15.63)	2.42 (2.25)	11.99 (11.53)
	1,3-DCB	15.55 (15.53)	2.39 (2.25)	11.60 (11.53)
	1,4-DCB	15.38 (15.53)	2.33 (2.25)	11.29 (11.53)
RuII	GN	14.70 (14.53)	3.63 (3.66)	16.44 (16.95)
	1,2-DCB	17.89 (19.61)	2.88 (3.13)	13.23 (16.01)
	1,3-DCB	18.55 (19.61)	3.09 (3.13)	14.57 (16.01)
	1,4-DCB	18.10 (19.61)	2.96 (3.13)	14.58 (16.01)

Isotopically labeled succinotrile complex ($Ru(NH_3)_5NCCH_2CH_2^{13}CN$)(PF_6)₂: The strategy adopted was to prepare $N^{13}CCH_2CH_2C(O)H$. Under suitable conditions it reacted⁵ with $Ru(NH_3)_5^{2+}$ to yield $[Ru(NH_3)_5NCCH_2CH_2^{13}CN]^{2+}$.

3-Bromo-1-propanol (0.25 m, 0.38 g) was dissolved in methanol (3 ml). $K^{13}CN$ (250 mg) was dissolved in H_2O (3 ml). The aqueous solution was then added dropwise to the methanol solution and the mixture refluxed for 8 h, after which it was cooled to room temperature and stirred overnight. It was then heated to 40° on a water-bath and aspirator suction applied to remove the methanol, suction being continued for 30 min after the solution had reached a constant volume. The solution was extracted with CH_2Cl_2 (4×5 ml). The methylene chloride solution was dried with $MgSO_4$, filtered and added to a flask containing pyridinium chlorochromate⁶ (500 mg). The solution was initially bright orange but darkened as the oxidation proceeded. After 1 h, the solution, now brown, was filtered, first through a coarse frit and then through a medium frit, to remove the gummy black chromium product.

The final step involved condensation of the aldehyde with ligand NH_3 . A solution of $[Ru(NH_3)_5]Cl_2$ (93 mg) in 0.1M NaOH (3 ml) was placed in a 50 ml bubbler flask. The methylene chloride containing the labelled aldehyde was then added to it. Air was bubbled vigorously through the flask to ensure mixing. After 25 min the mixture was filtered and the aqueous layer separated. A solution of NH_4PF_6 (500 mg) in H_2O (3 ml) was added to the aqueous solution. It was then cooled in the refrigerator for 0.5 h and the resulting solid was filtered and recrystallised from warm H_2O to give brownish yellow product (~ 10 mg).

Infrared spectra: The infrared spectra were obtained using an IBM IR/98 Fourier transform infrared spectrometer. Computer software made it possible to plot the spectra in either the transmittance or absorbance mode. Spectra were typically obtained from 32 scans of the region 4 000–500 cm^{-1} , but in a few cases 200 scans were used.

Each spectrum was calculated from two single beam experiments, one a reference with no sample present. The sample chamber was thoroughly flushed with nitrogen before and during collection of the reference and sample spectra. The flushing was necessary to eliminate extraneous peaks at about 2 400 cm^{-1} resulting from atmospheric carbon dioxide. The parameters used in collecting the spectra led to a resolution of 2 cm^{-1} . For some of the samples, the resolution was 1 cm^{-1} , but this change made very little difference in the observed spectra. The band-widths at half-maximum of the nitrile peaks were typically 10 cm^{-1} or greater so that distortion of band shapes and consequent inaccuracies in integrated intensities be small.

The samples were prepared as 13 mm KBr pellets with about 1 mg of compound in 200 mg of

KBr. The osmium(II) pellets were prepared in 9 mm screw type pellet presses and were kept under argon until the spectra were obtained.

Raman spectra: The Raman spectra were obtained with a Spex Monochromator using the 5145 Å line of an argon laser. The powdered samples were held in 1.5 mm glass capillaries. (The spectra were recorded by C. Peterson, whose assistance is gratefully acknowledged.)

Microanalyses were performed by Stanford Microanalytical Laboratory.

Results

The frequencies observed for the nitrile peaks are compiled in Table 2. Included as well are literature

data for $[Co(NH_3)_4(H_2O)NC-C_6H_4-CN](CF_3SO_3)_2^+$, $[Co(NH_3)_5FN](PF_6)_3^-$ and $[Ru(NH_3)_5FN](PF_6)_3^-$.

TABLE 2—INFRARED STRETCHING FREQUENCIES (cm⁻¹) FOR BOUND AND REMOTE NITRILE GROUPS^a

Metal	Ligand	ν_{bound}	ν_{remote}	ν_{free}^b	$\Delta\nu$ ($\nu_{bound} - \nu_{remote}$)
CrIII	GN	2 311	2 252	2 257 ^b	59
	CoIII	GN	2 324	2 251	2 257 ^b
CoIII	1,2-DCB	2 301	2 247	2 237	54
	1,3-DCB	2 300	2 240	2 234	60
	1,4-DCB	2 308	2 236	2 232	72
	LBO ^c	2 310	2 240	2 240	70
	FN ^d	2 302	2 240	2 240	62
RhIII	GN	2 327	2 251	2 257 ^b	76
	1,2-DCB	2 299	2 247	2 237	52
	1,3-DCB	2 300	2 240	2 234	60
	1,4-DCB	2 306	2 235	2 232	71
IrIII	GN	2 300	2 252	2 257 ^b	48
	1,2-DCB	2 290	2 245	2 237	45
	1,3-DCB	2 295	2 240	2 234	55
	1,4-DCB	2 288	2 243	2 232	45
RuIII	GN	2 310	2 251	2 257 ^b	59
	1,2-DCB	2 280	2 246	2 237	34
	1,3-DCB	2 282	2 240	2 234	42
	1,4-DCB	2 284	2 235	2 232	49
OsIII	GN	2 283	2 252	2 257 ^b	31
	1,2-DCB	(2 251) ^e	2 240	2 237	(11) ^f
	1,3-DCB	2 258	2 240	2 234	18
	1,4-DCB	(2 254) ^e	2 233	2 232	(21) ^f
RuII	GN	2 252	2 252	2 257 ^b	0
	1,2-DCB	2 182	2 223	2 237	-46
	1,3-DCB	2 201	2 236	2 234	-35
	1,4-DCB	2 183	2 230	2 232	-42
	FN ^g	2 182	2 228	2 240	-46
OsII	GN	2 183	2 255	2 257 ^b	-72
	1,2-DCB	2 120	2 234	2 237	-114
	1,3-DCB	2 125	2 233	2 234	-103
	1,4-DCB	2 128	2 225	2 232	-97

^aUncoordinated ligand. ^bIn CHCl₃ sol. ^cRef. 7; CF₃SO₃ salt. ^dRef. 8; as PF₆ salt. ^eNot observed. ^fDifference calculated using the frequency for the bound nitrile as determined by Raman spectroscopy (see Table 3). ^gRef. 9; as FF₆ salt.

In most cases two peaks are observed, one close to that recorded for the free dinitrile, and thus assigned to the remote C≡N group in the complex.

In the cases of 1,2-DCB and 1,4-DCB as ligands on Os^{III}, only a single ir band in the nitrile region is observed. Because for GN and 1,3-DCB as ligands, separate absorptions for bound nitrile is observed, but of very low intensity, it seemed likely that the failure to observe separate peaks in the first two cases is partly at least a matter of low intensity rather than only of peak coincidence and so Raman spectra were taken to determine the frequencies of the missing peaks. The results are shown in Table 3. In each of the three cases, a single absorption is observed, different from that assigned to the free nitrile group in the ir spectrum. The agreement for the bound nitrile peak in the case of 1,3-DCB, 2 258

TABLE 3—RAMAN FREQUENCIES (cm⁻¹) OF BOUND NITRILE GROUPS IN OSMIUM(III) PENTAAMMINE DICYANOBENZENE COMPLEXES

Compd.	(ON)
[Os(NH ₃) ₅ (1,2-DCB)](CF ₃ SO ₃) ₂	2 251
[Os(NH ₃) ₅ (1,3-DCB)](CF ₃ SO ₃) ₂	2 262
[Os(NH ₃) ₅ (1,4-DCB)](CF ₃ SO ₃) ₂	2 254

cm⁻¹ in the ir and 2 262 cm⁻¹ in the Raman, is not perfect, but because the maximum of the peak in the Raman spectrum is not clearly resolved due to noise, it is no cause for concern. In none of the Raman spectra is the peak corresponding to the remote nitrile group observed. The peaks for the bound nitrile are broad and overlap those expected for the remote nitriles; these being of considerably lower intensity are hidden.

It should be noted that the Raman spectra were obtained from the solids in powder form, whereas for the ir spectra the compounds were dispersed in KBr pellets. To test the magnitude of an effect ascribable to a difference in medium, an infrared spectrum of the 1,3-DCB complex of Os^{III} was obtained on the solid which had been dispersed on a sodium chloride plate by evaporation from an acetone solution. The peak of the remote nitrile group appeared at a frequency 1 cm⁻¹ lower than that observed in a KBr pellet.

A matter of considerable consequence is the degree of coupling of the bound and remote nitrile groups. This can be assessed from an examination of the ir spectra of the free dinitrile themselves. Where the extent of coupling is substantial and where the symmetric combination is not excluded on symmetry grounds (for our ligands this is the case only for 1,4-dicyanobenzene), separate signals for the symmetric and asymmetric combinations will be observed. This is in fact the case for malononitrile, where two bands are observed but even in this case they are separated by only 5 cm⁻¹. For all of the nitriles we have used, only a single band is observed, down to a resolution of 1 cm⁻¹. We conclude therefore that the coupling in the compounds we have studied is not a serious perturbation, the more so because it is expected to be smaller when the two nitriles are made dissimilar, as in our mononuclear

Fig. 1. Infrared spectrum of $[\text{Ru}(\text{NH}_3)_5(\text{NOCH}_2\text{OH}, ^{13}\text{C}^{15}\text{N})](\text{PF}_6)_3$.

TABLE 4—RATIOS OF INTEGRATED INTENSITIES OF BOUND AND REMOTE NITRILE PEAKS (BOUND/REMOTE) FOR METAL PENTAAMMINE DINITRILE COMPLEXES

Ligand	Cr ^{III}	Co ^{III}	Rh ^{III}	Ir ^{III}	Ru ^{III}	Os ^{III}	Ru ^{II}	Os ^{II}
Glutaronitrile	4.6	2.4	1.9	0.32	1.8	0.62	(b)	2.1
1,2-Dicyanobenzene	—	6.7	3.8	0.54	1.7	(a)	13	8.3
1,3-Dicyanobenzene	—	3.9	2.2	0.61	1.6	0.55	22	5.5
1,4-Dicyanobenzene	—	3.4	1.3	0.36	0.7	(a)	12	2.0

(a) = Bound nitrile peak not observed. (b) = Bound and remote nitrile peaks coincide.

complexes, than when the nitriles are equivalent, as in the free ligands.

This conclusion is further supported by the results of the isotopic experiment done with the succinonitrile complex of Ru^{II} in which the remote nitrile group was labelled with ^{13}C . In the parent complex, only a single band is observed; on changing the mass of one of the atoms in the vibrating groups, two new frequencies are expected if coupling is extensive, but if it is weak, one band is expected to remain (almost) unchanged and the second to appear at a lower frequency.

The parent complex shows a band at 2252 cm^{-1} , but it is rather broad, this alone indicating that we are dealing with composite absorption. In the labelled complex (Fig. 1) a peak of lower intensity appears at 2219 cm^{-1} , while a more intense nitrile feature now appears at 2244 cm^{-1} . The peak at 2219 cm^{-1} can be ascribed to the remote nitrile group.

When the mass difference is taken into account in the simplest way, that is by treating the CN group as an independent unit, the stretching vibration for the remote nitrile on the parent complex is calculated to appear at 2266 cm^{-1} . Because of kinematic coupling in the real case, the actual shift will be somewhat less. The profile observed in the parent complex is consistent with there being a strong component at ca. 2244 cm^{-1} , and a weaker component at a frequency somewhat less than 2266 cm^{-1} .

In Table 4 are summarised the results on the integrated intensity of the bound nitrile compared to that of the remote. The intensity ratios were determined from absorbance vs frequency plots of the nitrile region of the spectrum. Peak areas were determined by tracing the peaks onto a sheet of paper, cutting and weighing the cuttings. The spectra were found to be reproducible when separated samples of the complexes were used.

In Fig. 2 are shown some extremes in the response of the IR spectra to changes in the metal ion, with respect both to shifts and intensities, for a common ligand, 1,4-DCB. In the rhodium complex, the band for the bound nitrile is at higher energy, and it has somewhat higher intensity than does the remote group. In the Os^{III} complex, there is no hint of a band for the bound nitrile, which according to the Raman spectrum, should appear at 2254 cm^{-1} . In the Os^{II} complex, the band for the bound nitrile appears at lower energy than that for the remote and is of much greater intensity.

Fig. 2. In spectra: (A) $[\text{Rh}(\text{NH}_3)_5(1,4\text{-DCB})](\text{CF}_3\text{SO}_3)_2$, (B) $[\text{Os}^{\text{III}}(\text{NH}_3)_5(1,4\text{-DCB})](\text{CF}_3\text{SO}_3)_2$ and (C) $[\text{Os}^{\text{II}}(\text{NH}_3)_5(1,4\text{-DCB})](\text{CF}_3\text{SO}_3)_2$.

The most serious source of errors in the values of the ratios arises in estimating the areas of overlapping peaks, these errors being greatest in the Os^{III} and Ru^{II} cases, where a small peak overlaps with a considerably larger one. In these cases the larger

peak was extrapolated to the base line in the overlapping region. It was assumed that the absorption band is symmetrical, and the resolved segment of the band was used to define the profile in the overlapping region. The area of the small peak was then taken as that remaining. When the two peaks are well separated, the error in the measurement of the peak areas probably does not exceed ten percent, but where there is serious overlap, as for Os^{II} , Os^{III} and Ru^{II} species, the error in the ratios may be as high as a factor of 2.

Discussion

The general framework for understanding the frequency shifts has been laid by earlier work with nitriles as well as with other similar ligands which engage in back-bonding interactions with appropriate metal ions. The present work differs from much of the earlier work in that, by using mononuclear dinitriles, shifts for a bound nitrile relative to an unnumbered nitrile are measured in the same medium. The medium effects are admittedly not large. As can be seen from the fact that where two well-resolved peaks for the complexes are observed, one, measured in a crystalline salt, is close to that observed for the ligand as a pure phase, the difference in no case being greater than 11 cm^{-1} . It is nevertheless a significant advantage to have eliminated this as a variable.

Three effects are commonly considered in discussing shifts: a purely mechanical effect arising from the bond established between the donor nitrogen and the metal atom (kinematic coupling); an electronic effect arising from engaging the lone pair in a σ bond to the metal ion; a second electronic effect arising from delocalisation of π electron density into the π^* orbitals of the ligand.

Purcell and Drago¹⁰ examined the magnitude of the kinematic effect for acetonitrile bound to Lewis acids (A), such as BF_3 and SnCl_4 . The $\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ frequency is raised, the shift increases with increased force constant for the $\text{A}-\text{N}\equiv\text{C}$ bond and it becomes essentially independent of the mass of the attached atom above a mass of 12. An estimate was made of the effect expected for our systems, when the force constant for the metal-N stretch is taken to be the same as it is in $\text{Pt}(\text{CH}_3\text{CN})_2\text{Cl}_2$, namely $4.05\text{ mdyne \AA}^{-1}$. The result, an increase in frequency over a free nitrile functionality of 50 cm^{-1} , is essentially independent of mass for the range of metal ions we have studied. The shift does depend on the metal-N stretching force constant, which is not known for our species. Because of the lower coordination number of the Pt^{II} complex compared to those we have dealt, the value of 4.5 is likely a reasonably good estimate of the force constants even for tripositive ions. Again, because of increased back-bonding in the complexes with Ru^{II} and Os^{II} , there will be compensation for the increased coordination number compared to Pt^{II} by back-bonding which strengthens the metal-N band. At any rate,

it seems likely that the kinematic effect will be reasonably constant throughout the series and will not seriously obscure other effects.

An effect on the $N\equiv C$ stretching frequency of σ bond formation to a Lewis acid has also been noted (as it has for other ligands such as CO) and LCAO-MO calculations on Lewis acid adducts of acetonitrile have been performed by Purcell and Drago¹⁰. The calculations showed that on complexation, there is net electron transfer to the Lewis acid from both carbon and nitrogen of the nitrile. This leads to a lowering of both the σ and π orbitals in the nitrile, the dominant contribution to the increase in frequency coming from a strengthened σ interaction between carbon and nitrogen.

The greatest effects observed on intra-ligand frequencies for π -acid ligands such as nitriles and carbon monoxide arise from back-bonding. Clarke and Ford^{12,13} were the first to prepare nitrile complexes of pentaammineruthenium(II). They noted a correlation between frequency lowering and the capacity of the ligand to extract πd electron density from the metal, recording shifts as great as 100 cm^{-1} in some cases. Of the metal centers we have used, these effects are greatest for Os^{II} followed by Ru^{II} . The effects observed for Ru^{II} with the different nitriles closely follow expectations based on changes in the energy of the lowest lying π^* orbital of the ligand. Thus the decrease in frequency is greater for 1,3-DCB than it is for GN. In 1,3-DCB, the two nitriles are only weakly conjugated and the lowering of the energy of the π orbital can be ascribed to the electron-withdrawing effect of $-C_6H_4C\equiv N$. The decreases in frequency for 1,2-DCB and 1,4-DCB are greater than that for the 1,3-isomer, because having the two $C\equiv N$ in conjugation is expected to lower the energy of the π^* orbital. Surprisingly, though the decreases in frequency are greater for the corresponding Os^{II} complexes, as expected because of the much greater propensity of Os^{II} for back-bonding, the pattern within the group is different from that observed for Ru^{II} , and not so readily rationalised. In the first place the difference in shift for 1,3-DCB compared to GN recorded in the case of Os^{II} is not significantly greater than that for Ru^{II} despite the well-recognised greater tendency of Os^{II} to transfer πd electron density to a π acid ligand. Moreover, the shifts for 1,2-DCB and 1,4-DCB, -114 and -97 respectively, are not clearly greater than they are for 1,3-DCB (-108). These differences between Ru^{II} and Os^{II} go beyond possible errors in measurement and suggest that when back-bonding becomes strong, effects arise which are as yet not understood.

We will turn now to a consideration of the shift data as a function of the properties of the metal centers, and will consider first those for which back-bonding is a minor effect. Chemical behaviour provides no reason to invoke such effects in understanding the chemistry of Cr^{III} , Co^{III} , Rh^{III} , Ru^{III} or Ir^{III} . To the extent that there nevertheless is a

contribution, on the basis of general experience in the isoelectronic series Co^{III} , Rh^{III} , Ir^{III} , it is expected to increase in the order given. To a remarkable degree, the shifts for the first two agree, and they are larger than they are for Ir^{III} . It seems likely that the large positive shifts for the first two reflect the influence primarily only of the first two factors mentioned in the introduction, and that for Ir^{III} , some influence of back-bonding is felt.

Comparisons of Co^{III} with Cr^{III} and Ru^{III} are difficult to make, because of the differences in the electronic structure $-\pi d^6$, πd^6 and πd^5 respectively. Nevertheless, the fact that the shifts are consistently lower for Ru^{III} than that for the neighbouring element Rh^{III} finds a simple rationalisation. Charge transfer from ligand to Ru^{III} is often invoked to explain the properties of Ru^{III} complexes. For example, $(NH_3)_5RuBr^{2+}$ is strongly colored while the corresponding rhodium complex is not. Ligand to metal charge transfer occurs at much lower energies for Ru^{III} than for Rh^{III} , because only the former has an electron vacancy in the πd orbitals. Charge transfer from a bonding ligand orbital to the vacancy in the πd orbital of Ru^{III} can also explain the weakening of the $C=N$ bond in the Ru^{III} complex relative to the Rh^{III} .

In terms of electronic structure, Os^{III} bears the same relation to Ir^{III} that Ru^{III} bears to Rh^{III} . It is to be noted that $\Delta\nu$ for Os^{III} is smaller than that for Ir^{III} just as it is smaller for Ru^{III} than for Rh^{III} . It is quite unlikely however that the relationship arises from the same cause in the two cases. If it involves ligand to metal charge transfer, then, contrary to fact, the difference between $\Delta\nu$ for Os^{III} and Ir^{III} is expected to be less than between Ru^{III} and Rh^{III} — Os^{III} is a much weaker electron acceptor than is Ru^{III} . There is a body of chemical evidence supporting the conclusion that π back-bonding is a significant effect for Os^{III} . For example, a stable complex of Os^{III} with CO has been prepared, and osmium ammine complexes with N_6 persist long enough to make characterisation possible¹⁴. Moreover, while Ru^{III} or Co^{III} strongly activates coordinated nitriles for hydrolysis, this is not the case for Os^{III} ¹⁵. Thus, we incline to the conclusion that the major cause of the shift in the $C\equiv N$ stretch to lower frequencies for Os^{III} compared to Ir^{III} is caused by the greater degree of back-bonding for the former. That back-bonding is more prominent for Os^{III} than for Ir^{III} is expected on simple theoretical grounds because the effective nuclear charge acting on the valence electrons is greater for the latter.

Back-bonding becomes the dominant effect for Ru^{II} and Os^{II} , and more than compensates for the two effects which tend to raise $\nu_{C\equiv N}$ when nitriles form complexes. As already mentioned, back-bonding effects are much greater for Os^{II} than for Ru^{II} , and the greater shift observed in the Os^{II} complexes is quite in harmony with the expectation.

In discussing the intensity data we begin by noting that there is a correlation between the shift

and the intensity data. For convenience, the two sets of data are reproduced in Table 5, where we have chosen for first consideration the observations made with 1,4-dicyanobenzene, because, of the

TABLE 5							
Metal ion	Co ^{III}	Rh ^{III}	Ru ^{III}	Ir ^{III}	Os ^{III}	Ru ^{II}	Os ^{II}
$\Delta\nu$, cm ⁻¹	73	71	49	45	21	-42	-97
Intensity ratio	3.4	1.3	0.7	0.96	<0.03	12	20

ligands we have investigated, they show the greatest contrast in the intensities.

When the values of $\Delta\nu$ are arranged in order from the most positive to the most negative, the intensity ratios are observed to decrease to a minimum, and then to increase sharply when the shifts become negative. In discussing the change in $\Delta\nu$ with change in the properties of the metal ion, it was concluded that electronic factors, i.e. changes in the mode of interaction of metal ion with the ligand, could account at least qualitatively for the results. Similar factors appear sufficient to rationalise gross features of the intensity data.

It is to be noted that the integrated intensity, A_1 of an infrared band is governed by the proportionality,

$$A_1 \propto (d\mu/dQ_1)^2$$

namely, by the square of the gradient of the dipole moment with respect to the amplitude of the vibration, where the gradient is evaluated at the equilibrium configuration. The negative shifts are attributed to back-bonding, and back-bonding can account for the dramatic rise in intensity noted for Ru^{II} and for Os^{II}. According to calculations made by Kettle¹⁶ for CO as ligand, across the range of bond length change in a vibration, σ overlap in the valence orbitals of the ligand remains nearly constant, but the π overlap decreases significantly. The same conclusion presumably applies to the triple bond in the nitrile. As the CN bond stretches the π^* orbitals are lowered in energy. Where back-bonding is significant, this leads to net electron flow from metal to ligand, generating a contribution to the dipole with the positive end on the metal and the negative end on the ligand. The effect is further enhanced because as the N \equiv C bond lengthens, the metal-N distance decreases, thereby increasing the overlap of the $\pi d-\pi^*$ orbitals.

Back-bonding however cannot explain the increase in intensity noted from the low minimum at Os^{III} to ions at the beginning of the series, ions which according to experience, and according to general theoretical arguments, have a very weak capacity for back-bonding. Intuitively it is expected that in placing a Lewis acid on the N atom of the nitrile, the resonance form $^-:N=C:^+$ will be favored, and unless there is a compensating flow of electron density from nitrogen to carbon as the

C-N bond stretches, this will result in an increase in the dipole moment gradient. At any rate, by invoking some effect of this kind for the cations and by taking into account the decreasing contribution of back-bonding as we move to the left of Os^{III} in the series, for the most part the relative order is accounted for. The dipole moment generated by the cations absent back-bonding opposes that generated by back-bonding, and we infer that for Os^{III} in some cases, they effectively cancel. The operation of the effects which have been described is portrayed in Fig. 3.

The most prominent feature of the intensity data we have observed has been noted also for other π -acid ligands: with metal ions that lend themselves

Fig. 3. Model of electron flow during nitrile stretching vibration. Upper white arrow represents flow of back-bonding electrons from metal to ligand. Lower white arrow represents flow of electrons within ligand. Black arrow represents not electron flow.

to back-bonding interactions, there is an enhancement of intensity, and this can become the major factor in affecting the intensity. Another prominent feature of our data is the very low values of intensity which can occur for Os^{III} and which we have accounted for by an interaction which has an effect on the dipole gradient opposite in sign to that resulting from back-bonding. These two features are preserved for the other three ligands. In every case there is a rise in intensity toward the end of the series, and in every case the minimum in intensity is observed in the Os^{III} complex. For Os^{III} with both 1,2-DCB and 1,4-DCB, the band corresponding to the stretching frequency does not arise above the level of noise, and in these two cases there must be an almost exact cancellation of the opposing effects referred to.

While the general degree of consistency is satisfying, a closer examination of the data shows that much remains to be explained, particularly for the ions where back-bonding is not an important interaction. Certainly the idea which was introduced to account for the rise in the intensity ratio to the left of the minimum is too simple. Hush and Williams¹⁷ used a self-consistent field treatment to calculate the effect on the frequency and intensity of the C—O stretch in carbon monoxide of an electric field directed along the C—O axis. They find, starting with the highest fields, an increase in frequency to a maximum, followed then by a decrease. The intensity ratio, field/zero field, decreases as the field strength decreases, reaching a minimum at a field strength somewhat greater than that which corresponds to the maximum in the frequencies. It is difficult to fit this treatment to our data as a whole, nor, because we are dealing with a different ligand can a fit be expected. But it does appear from examining the data that if field is defined by radius and charge of the ions, important details are not accounted for. Thus Cr^{III} and Co^{III} by virtue of similar size and identical charges would be expected to have much the same effect on the intensity. In the single case, GN, in which the Cr^{III} complex was prepared, the intensity ratio for Cr^{III} (πd^3) is almost twice as great as it is for Co^{III} (πd^6). There are significant differences also between Ru^{III} and Rh^{III} in respect to both intensity ratio and frequencies, and a very great difference between Ir^{III} and Os^{III} in the matter of intensities. It does appear that the electronic structures of the metal ions need explicitly to be taken into account.

Though the effects of back-bonding seem to be clearly exposed in these and in other studies, they are far from understood. While the smaller enhancement in the intensity ratio for GN on the one hand, and the DCB group on the other, is expected, the effects observed within the DCB group are not accounted for simply by invoking differences in extent of back-bonding, presumed to be greater for 1,2-DCB or 1,4-DCB than for 1,3-DCB. In fact, both for Ru^{II} and Os^{II}, the greatest enhancement in intensity is observed for 1,3-DCB. The differences in the enhancement of intensity for the various π -acid ligands, is as striking as the enhancement itself.

Further work with nitrile ligands is clearly desirable. Though they are more complicated than

the much studied carbon monoxide, they offer clear advantages. One is that in being more nucleophilic than CO, complexes over a wider range of oxidation state for a particular metal with a particular set of auxiliary ligands can be prepared. In particular, for the pentaammine series, it may be possible to prepare the nitrile complex of Pt^{IV}, thus extending the range of oxidation states in the less well-understood regime. Moreover, the fact that the oscillator is attached to an organic group, which might be regarded as a disadvantage, can be considered to be an asset, because valuable information can be obtained by varying the properties of this group in a systematic way.

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